

NEUMO HEALTH AND ENVIRONMENT

LUNGS

These sheep lungs have been plastinated in order to preserve their natural aspect and maximum size (Inspiration). The internal space (lumen) of the bronchii is preserved to allow the exploration of the bronchial tree with an endoscope.

This specimen includes the trachea, two main bronchii and the different lobar bronchii. It also includes the pulmonary parenchyma. The right lung has four lobes: cranial/superior (divided in two portions), middle, caudal/inferior and accessory (not present in human). The left lung has two lobes: cranial/superior (divided in two portions) and caudal/inferior.

Each lobe of both lungs has its own lobar bronchii. The lobar bronchii of the cranial lobe of the right lung is the only one that arises directly from the trachea through the tracheal bronchii. This bronchii is exclusive of ruminants and pigs.

1. Trachea. 2. Cranial (superior) right lobe (cranial part). 3. Cranial (superior) right lobe (caudal part). 4. Middle lobe. 5. Caudal (inferior) right lobe. 6. Cranial (superior) left lobe. 7. Caudal (inferior) left lobe.

BRONCHIAL TREE

The trachea is divided into the right and left primary bronchi. These bronchi divide into lobar bronchi with secondary bronchi, tertiary bronchi, bronchioles, alveolar ducts and alveoli. All these air passageways are known as the bronchial tree. It is important that students realize how the air follows the pathway towards the alveoli, where the gas exchange occurs.

1. Trachea. 2. Right primary bronchi. 3. Left primary bronchi. 4. Right tracheal bronchi. 5. Secondary bronchi. 6. Bronchioles and alveolar ducts.

TRANSPARENT SECTION OF THE LUNG

This section displays the tissues of the lungs. Bronchioles and alveoli are clearly seen. Also blood vessels, which are necessary for the gas exchange. This is facilitated by the very thin wall of the alveoli which is surrounded by blood vessels.

1. Alveoli. 2. Bronchi. 3. Bronchioli. 4. Vessel

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